

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation
agendas and support in 4EU+

H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020

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Description of the deliverable

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D7.3 DEC Plan Second update (M35)

The plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication of results of the H2020 project Transforming ReseArch & INnovation agendas and support in 4EU+ (TRAIN4EU) is a work in progress that evolves as the TRAIN4EU project develops. The draft TRAIN4EU DEC plan and the tentative Implementation Plan (annex I) are in that respect designed to be subject to adjustments and revisions as new opportunities and insights arise during the project's life. The list of tentative DEC activities will be adjusted accordingly in the DEC plan first and second update (M24 & M35).

The DEC plan sets up objectives and contains concrete plans for DEC activities, including management and monitoring of the activities.

The dissemination, exploitation and communication activities during the project's life and beyond are decided and conducted in an ongoing co-creative and transparent process between the Alliance partners and in dialogue with internal and external stakeholders to ensure TRAIN4EU contribution to the transformation of the European research and education agenda.

Figure 1. Overview of TRAIN4EU governance, with change of coordinator in M20

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1. Introduction

The DEC Plan's main text is preserved in the first and second update. Only minor updates and textual revisions have been made to reflect the development of TRAIN4EU.

TRAIN4EU aims to demonstrate that it is possible to leverage the potential of the 4EU collaboration even better by integrating research, innovation and service to society into the Alliance. Moreover, TRAIN4EU will explore and demonstrate how to link collaboration on research, innovation and societal dimensions in multiple ways to the collaborative work already developed in the Alliance.

By sharing best practices, new methods and new ideas within R&I support during the project's lifespan and beyond, a common ground will be established, and synergies unlocked between the partners of the Alliance. TRAIN4EU will take international university collaboration and co-creation to the next level with a comprehensive approach, covering all missions of a university. A true transformation of how things are done in the daily university business.

A thorough strategy and a plan for widespread dissemination, exploitation and communication of project results and recommendations are not only essential for the project's concrete impact and embedment but also for the overall aim to transform the research and innovation agendas and support in the 4EU+ Alliance as well as enhance the role of universities in the European research and higher education area.

The dissemination, exploitation and communication activities of TRAIN4EU will undoubtedly be subject to change as the project unfolds and materialize during its lifetime.

The structure of this DEC plan has been adjusted in accordance with Deliverable 7.2 DEC Plan first update (M24) and with Deliverable 7.3 DEC Plan second update (M35).

The DEC plan for the TRAIN4EU project has been formulated in accordance with the EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms definition on dissemination, exploitation and communication¹:

Dissemination: The public disclosure of results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation: The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

Communication: Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3bb7278e-ebf3-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

1.1 Shaping the TRAIN4EU DEC plan

The core purposes of this DEC plan are:

- Outlining relevant objectives for communication activities within the TRAIN4EU project
- Ensuring that the planned DEC activities are timely and relevant for the vision of the broader 4EU+ Alliance and connect to the European transformation agenda
- Setting up a framework for managing and monitoring the DEC activities

The draft DEC plan is designed to be subject to adjustments and revisions as new opportunities and insights arise during the project's life. However, unforeseen circumstances such as the COVID-19 pandemic can affect the implementation of physical DEC activities as described. A significant number of DEC activities are online, but in case planned physical activities cannot be implemented, a contingency plan will be put in place in phase II of the implementation plan (see annex 1).

The design of this DEC plan has a two-pronged approach. On the one hand it is a reflection on the process of shaping a DEC plan, setting up objectives and selecting means, on the other hand it contains concrete plans for DEC activities, including (plans for) management and monitoring of such activities. The draft is both a tool for sustained reflection on the development of the TRAIN4EU project and the DEC activities, as well as a tangible tool for the Work Package 7 (WP) management to monitor the progression of the DEC plan.

Risk management and implementation

The most significant challenge in creating the draft DEC plan at this point in the project is the interdependence between the findings of the WPs and the plans for dissemination and communication of these findings, as the DEC draft is designed before the actual findings materialise. The strategy is to design a DEC plan that is adaptable to as yet unknown findings.

Internal and external factors such as delays or change of scope in each WP can cause delays. A close cooperation between WP7, WP6 and WP8 as well as regular meetings in the Steering Committee with participation of WP7 alongside the other WPs will ensure that unforeseen or expected delays in the deliverables and a change of scope in each WP will come to light and be incorporated in an adjusted DEC plan. The design of the TRAIN4EU project structure ensures that WP7 is part of the engine room.

Despite the COVID-19 pandemic the Alliance managed to continue and even widen its high level of activity, relying on remote or hybrid solutions as an alternative to the planned physical DEC activities. Activities includes setting up an Academic Council with participation of students and researchers from all member universities, establishing a legal entity in April 2021 and holding a virtual high-level Annual Meeting during lockdown in November 2020. On top of that, meetings have been held continuously at all levels of 4EU+ governance as well as in working groups and task forces. Furthermore, 4EU+ has been the frame for numerous online conferences, workshops and summer schools for students, doctoral candidates and staff, 61 educational projects and 29 mini-grant initiatives carried out within the four 4EU+ Flagships with adjusted scopes, 259 online courses made available to students by 4EU+ universities and regular communication activities with the 4EU+ website attracting 52,000 unique visitors between November 2019 and April 2021.

The Alliance's H2020 SwafS project, TRAIN4EU, was born and brought up digitally. While still in its early years, a preliminary and tentative conclusion based on a flourishing collaboration between the Alliance partners is that building up a whole new project completely online is definitely possible and might even guarantee faster, more agile and co-creative development of the project.

The digital possibilities and the willingness of the Alliance partners to exploit them serve as inspiration for the DEC plan and set an example for the implementation of the DEC plan regardless of any current or future circumstances.

The dissemination and communication activities are built on a stakeholder mapping, a decision on initial dissemination activities based on the conclusions in the WP protocols and setting tentative ambitions for the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. All this is based on a co-creative and transparent process organised as bilateral ad hoc dialogues and meetings between WP7 and WP1-6 leaders with the latter as the main content contributors.

2. Objectives of the TRAIN4EU DEC Plan

The DEC objectives for the TRAIN4EU project outlined in the GA Description of Action are:

- To ensure widespread dissemination of project outcomes both internally across the Alliance partners and externally to other European University alliances, national policymakers, business sectors and the European Commission as well as broad dissemination to other universities through the consortium's participation in international university organisations (LERU, LERU-CE7, EUA, IARU, etc.).
- Based on the outcomes, briefs, reports etc. will be prepared aimed at the various external stakeholders, which can form the basis of further exploitation outside the 4EU+ Alliance.
- To ensure widespread knowledge and support for TRAIN4EU by engaging external and internal stakeholders in dialogue from the beginning of the project, serving the dual purpose of gaining attention and support, and providing us with valuable views and input on project plans and aims.

On the basis of these objectives, three overarching objectives for the DEC plan are defined:

- Raising awareness about the value and potential of TRAIN4EU among internal and external stakeholders to secure widespread knowledge and support for TRAIN4EU.
- Widespread internal and external dissemination of project outcomes to European and international universities, policymakers, business sectors and the European Commission.
- Exploitation of project outcomes in the form of mutual learning exercises and active sharing and adaptation of best practices.

Specific objectives to achieve the overarching objectives of the DEC Plan

- Creating an overview of target groups and stakeholders via stakeholder mapping
- Clear, focused and targeted communication
- Synergy and coherence with 4EU+ mission, 4EU+ communication policy and platforms
- Synergy and coherence with relevant 4EU+ activities, including those of the Erasmus+ European University project
- Supporting, managing, monitoring and following-up on dissemination activities
- Development of applicable key messages used in all communication activities

WP7 coordinates and oversees compliance of the specific objectives in an effort to realise the implementation plan and ensure the link between the three overarching objectives of the DEC Plan and the specific objectives. WP1-6 leaders will generate the content and more in-depth knowledge in terms of identification of target groups and development of key messages.

To ensure a transparent and co-creative approach in meeting the DEC objectives, the WP1-6 leaders, in joint cooperation with WP7, decide on the dissemination activities and set ambitions for the expected outcome of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities.

2.1 Synergy with 4EU+ communication

The DEC activities of TRAIN4EU will be fully aligned with the 4EU+ communication policy, platforms and activities – as well as with its visual identity and templates – to ensure synergy and coherence with the Alliance's existing communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The TRAIN4EU DEC activities will be implemented in close coordination with the ongoing 4EU+ communication activities and aligned with the activities carried out within the EUP WP7: Dissemination and Sustainability of the Erasmus+ 'European Universities' project, as well as with other activities carried out by the 4EU+ Communications Working Group.

TRAIN4EU project representatives are already participating regularly in the meetings of 4EU+ Communications Group. With this alignment ensured, the DEC plan contributes to the aim of 4EU+ to become a comprehensive and coherent European University alliance.

4EU+ communication policy²

The communication will be guided by the same principles as for the 4EU+ communication:

- Open communication approach - sharing relevant 4EU+ information across university structures, ensuring it reaches the right recipients
- Proactive approach - stimulating interest in the Alliance and its activities among the members of each 4EU+ institution's community, engaging them in 4EU+ communication by acquainting them with 4EU+ communication channels and tools
- Co-creation approach - engaging 4EU+ staff and students in the collaborative development of 4EU+ content
- Relevance approach – creating and securing interest in the Alliance among the 4EU+ community by focusing on concrete and relevant information.

Due to the scope of TRAIN4EU as primarily a research support project, the target group focus is slightly different from the 4EU+ Alliance's broad audience and student focus.

Joint 4EU+ communication channels and tools

An important assessment parameter and a benchmarking tool for European University alliances, social media performance plays a significant role for 4EU+ communication. Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram are all part of 4EU+ social media communication. Based on the 4EU+ social media strategy and recent evaluations of how 4EU+ uses social media channels in terms of target groups and users, using the 4EU+ LinkedIn account is the obvious and preferable choice, which is why TRAIN4EU results are planned to be communicated mainly on LinkedIn. Twitter may also be used as an important channel for the communication of, for example, policy briefs.

² See Annex II

Besides social media, especially LinkedIn, the TRAIN4EU webpages on the 4EU+ website are a vital source of information and gateway to the TRAIN4EU project for a broad audience with different backgrounds, interests and needs. Maintaining the website updated throughout the project and even beyond is one of the most important tasks in the DEC plan. All social media activities regarding TRAIN4EU will refer to #TRAIN4EU.

To strengthen the web performance the following will be done, reflecting recommendations from the Periodic Review 1 (M1-18) REA report results and review meeting on 9. Sept. 2022:

- Point out main keywords – the words and phrases that makes it possible for people to find the site via a search engine
- Create a more precise and relevant texts
- SEO (search engine optimization): strong headlines, anchors (internal links to other parts of texts), strong external links, keywords in meta-texts (short relevant summary of the page)
- Shorter web text
- More visualized content
- Not necessarily chronology in text
- Bullets

Another key digital communication channel is emailing, including the 4EU+ newsletter, sent to members of the 4EU+ university communities, representatives of the European Commission and other higher education stakeholders; anyone interested can subscribe to the 4EU+ newsletter via a subscription option on the 4EU+ website, as well as targeted emails to specific stakeholders.

General Data Protecting Regulation

Deliverable 8.8 Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the data management life cycle within and beyond TRAIN4EU, aiming to develop and ensure good data management and focusing on data collection, processing and generation, methodologies and standards applied, data sharing as well as data curation and preservation. The DMP is updated twice during the project lifetime, in M23 (D8.9) & M35 (D8.10), to ensure continued compliance in terms of potential data developments.

Deliverable 9.1. POPD Requirement no. 2 *Ethics requirements* outlines how personal and sensitive data will be handled in TRAIN4EU, with a particular focus on General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance.

The DEC activities will follow the guidelines in the Data Management Plan and Ethics requirements, ensuring that the GDPR is respected in the implementation of the TRAIN4EU DEC plan.

2.2 Mutual learnings - joint collaborations

WP7 will work closely with WP6 to reach the DEC objectives as listed in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. Joint work will draw on the WP6 protocol to analyse and assess collaboration on R&I support functions across the six partner universities in 4EU+ emerging from WP1-5, to be submitted as Deliverable 6.1 Protocol, Governance for Joint Collaboration on 31 December 2021.

DEC objectives include disseminating project outcomes internally and across partner institutions as well as externally to stakeholders such as national policymakers, business sectors and the European

Commission, as well as broad dissemination to other universities through partners' participation in international university organisations such as LERU, LERU-CE7, EUA, IARU, etc.

Particular emphasis will be placed on DEC activities in relation to collaboration with the 41 European University alliances that obtained financial support from the European Commission in 2019 and 2020 calls. The aim is to contribute to the transformation and closer integration of the European Research and Education Area by designing and implementing dissemination activities together where outcomes, ideas and new best practices are shared across the European University alliances.

Already in the SwafS proposal preparation phase, TRAIN4EU liaised with the other 16 first-call European University alliances about future collaboration. To ensure collaboration across the SwafS projects, and enhance potential joint DEC activities, the WP6 leader, who is also TRAIN4EU project manager, is a member of the R&I subgroup of the Forum of European Universities (FOREU), which presently only includes the 17 first-call alliances. A focal area for discussion within the R&I subgroup has been evaluations of the H2020 SwafS call transformation modules as part of the EU led co-creation process of EU funding instruments for the rollout of European universities.

DEC collaboration with the other alliances – both the 17 first-call and the 24 second-call alliances – will focus on sharing best practice and known drivers of success, as well as sharing insights about barriers of a legal, financial and regulatory nature in order to develop mechanisms to minimise their effect on implementing transformation of R&I support functions. Activities might include seminars, workshops and other forms of exchanges, as well as Policy Dialogue Meetings with the European Commission, to ensure joint collaboration and learning across the European Universities alliances.

WP7 and WP6 will seek to engage both internal and external 4EU+ stakeholders through targeted messages, briefs, reports etc. to further exploit the joint learning across partners and European University alliances. Based on this joint learning process, organised and coordinated jointly by WP7 and WP6, and drawing on the policy briefs to be submitted as Deliverable 7.6 and 7.7, TRAIN4EU aims to produce a set of common lessons learned, transformation potentials and policy recommendations on how to enhance R&I collaborations among European universities.

3. Target groups and stakeholders for TRAIN4EU

Identification of defined target groups and stakeholders is one of the determining specific objectives to achieve the overarching objectives of this DEC Plan.

Target groups and stakeholders are defined according to the following categories³:

- External stakeholders and target groups:
 - European Commission
 - National and regional policy makers
 - European and international university alliances
 - National rector assemblies and university organisations
 - Associated partners of the 4EU+ Alliance
 - National funding agencies and private research foundations (primarily WP4)
 - Business funding agencies and investors (primarily WP4)

³ Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement (Description of the Action), p. 22.

- Competitiveness clusters
 - Financial auditors on national and European level
 - International and national associations of librarians and information management professionals
 - European research associations
- Internal stakeholders and target groups:
 - University leaders in the 4EU+ Alliance
 - 4EU+ Flagship Programme Committees
 - Researchers/teachers, students, doctoral candidates and staff

This list of stakeholders and (division of) target groups will serve as the backbone for the different types of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities.

The findings (and novelties) of TRAIN4EU are a response to the call and interest of the European Commission. However, for each product it will be carefully considered which of the stakeholders could have an interest in the findings and how to reach them.

The choice of communication channel for each dissemination and communication activity will be made from activity to activity and in close cooperation with WP leaders. WP7 also consults with the 4EU+ Communication Group, comprising alliance experts with in-depth knowledge and experience in the area of reaching specific target groups.

In order to focus communication and use the limited resources constructively, relevant stakeholders are identified, categorized and mapped as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. TRAIN4EU stakeholder mapping

4. WP7 overview

Figure 3. Overview of TRAIN4EU WP7 interactions

5. Communication and dissemination

According to EC definitions, communication is strategic and targeted promotion and information of a project and its results to diverse audiences through various kinds of communication channels, while dissemination is a matter of distribution of relevant findings and new knowledge produced within the project to specific stakeholders, who may have an interest in the potential use of such findings.

Dissemination and communication are two sides of the same coin when it comes to distributing the same kind of information using the same types of communication channels but differ in choice of channels and expected outcome and impact.

The distinction between communication and dissemination activities are elaborated in the concrete initiatives described in the DEC implementation plan (annex 1).

Successful communication and dissemination rely on defined ambitions, tools and time invested.

In phase II of the DEC implementation plan tentative ambitions for the outcome of dissemination, exploitation and communication were set.

WP7 coordinates and monitors communication and dissemination, produces content and ensures standards. However, each WP leader/Alliance partner is encouraged to communicate, disseminate, and exploit the project and its results in relation to local and national stakeholders in the different languages in accordance with their specific local context and institutional communication policies and practices.

The aim for each work package is to furnish at least one relevant case to disseminate through various stakeholder specific channels. Both communication and dissemination channels and

activities have to be customised according to the specific needs of the case for maximum impact. Customisation of communication and dissemination is done primarily by WP leaders and members, guided by the objectives and principles set up for the DEC and, when needed, in dialogue with WP7.

5.1 Planned activities

The dissemination and communication activities as well as choice of channels are continuously adjusted to match the results and outputs from WP1-5 & WP6 once they are realised. Results of the first midterm evaluation of the 4EU+ alliance, as well as mutual learnings shared among European University alliance partners, may affect the approach, type and implementation of the DEC activities.

As an effect of the TRAIN4EU periodic review meeting with REA on 9. September 2022, there is an increased focus on strengthening the web performance, as mentioned, and on ensuring the visibility of European Union's H2020 funding at the webpage.

Joint 4EU+ communication channels and activities may include some of the following:

- Use existing 4EU+ website and social media platforms
- News on TRAIN4EU on 4EU+ website
- Contribution to the 4EU+ periodical newsletter

Joint 4EU+ dissemination activities may include some of the following:

- Policy Dialogue Meetings with the European Commission
- 4EU+ visioning conference (final Erasmus+ 'European Universities' project conference) on promotion and dissemination of Erasmus+ and TRAIN4EU results
- Forum of European Universities R&I subgroup meetings and discussion fora

TRAIN4EU Communication and Dissemination activities may include some of the following:

- Policy briefs
- Newsletters, targeted to relevant stakeholders
- Workshops and seminars
- Webinars
- Participation in conferences, synergy meetings, president meetings etc. in and between European and international university alliances
- National, local dialogue with internal and external relevant stakeholders
- Publications/reports
- Development of key messages
- Use of #TRAIN4EU

Consistency in communication of project title

Synergy and coherence with the 4EU+ communication policy as well as a joint visual identity are complemented by asking all internal project partners to use the project title ‘Transforming Research and Innovation agendas and support in 4EU+’ in all communication tools, such as newsletters, websites, publications, conference materials, policy briefs etc. prior to the acronym ‘TRAIN4EU’. Once the initial phase of the communication activities has come to an end and relations and recognition between relevant stakeholders and the project are established, the acronym TRAIN4EU may be used without further reference to the full project title.

According to ‘Acknowledgement of EU funding guidelines’, the European Union logo and European Union’s H2020 emblem must be used in all publication, specifying that TRAIN4EU has received research funding from H2020 as well as acknowledging the overall EU contribution to the project.

Local languages – accessibility of language

In order to facilitate the dissemination, exploitation and communication efforts, relevant English-language written outcomes are translated and published in French, German, Czech, Polish, Danish and Italian by each partner in the TRAIN4EU project, eg. when it comes to dissemination and communication to non-academic national stakeholders.

Each partner in the TRAIN4EU project will be responsible for a translation of each deliverable in the DEC plan into their national language, thereby securing wider dissemination, exploitation and communication of the results of the TRAIN4EU project.

6. Exploitation

To exploit and ensure embeddedness of the project results the intention is to implement piloting transformative processes in the 4EU+ Alliance and beyond, develop policy advice for policy makers and, finally, support the 4EU+ vision of being a landmark for the European Higher Education and Research Area, contributing to future transformations on a more general European level.

The internal and external exploitation in the 4EU+ Alliance will be pursued to the fullest extent. The focus in the DEC implementation plan is exploitation of TRAIN4EU case studies of various support measures, outlining best practices and lessons learned for the benefit of other European University Alliances and the university sector as such. Another part of the external exploitation is the contribution to European-wide policies on European universities through policy recommendations.

The initial ideas on internal and external exploitation activities are:

- Piloting transformative processes in 4EU+
- Collaboration between European University Alliances on best practices, lessons learned etc.
- Policy advice and recommendations for policy makers, European Commission etc.
- Mutual learning exercises
- Proactive sharing and adaptation of best practices

The exploitation activities will be unfolded and elaborated where relevant in the first and second updates of the DEC plan (M24 & M35), as stated in the implementation plan.

7. Implementation & reporting

Management and Monitoring

The role of WP7 is to oversee that the planned dissemination, exploitation and communication proceed according to the DEC plan, and to facilitate the close cooperation and communication between WP7 and WP1-6 in terms of feedback on the latter's own dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. WP7 is in that respect considered as a kind of repository for communication and dissemination ideas.

The most important tool for monitoring the progress in the implementation of DEC activities is regular bilateral meetings and ad hoc dialogue with key DEC contributors, the WP leaders as well as the project management.

Regular updates from WP7 in terms of progression in the DEC plan to the management – WP8 – as well as coordination between WP6 and WP7 are also essential.

Both elements – the role of the WP7 to manage and monitor the proceedings according to the DEC plan as well as WP7's role and responsibility in feeding into the management of the TRAIN4EU project – are mapped in the following scheme.

Reporting schedule

To ensure transparency, involvement and co-ownership between WP7 and WP1-5 as well as timely and frequent reporting to and collaboration with WP6, WP8 and the TRAIN4EU Steering Committee, the scheme also serves as a reporting schedule.

The scheme is subject to change in order to meet any adjusted needs from the WP leaders, Steering Committee and project management during the project's lifetime.

Fora	Frequency	WP7 theme/agenda	Participants	Facilitation
TRAIN4EU Steering Committee Meeting	Twice a year	WP7 leader's update on progress in DEC plan	Coordinator and project manager, WP leaders	WP8
TRAIN4EU UCPH project team	Every other month	WP7 leader's update on progress in DEC plan	Coordinator and project manager, local UCPH WP contributors	WP8
WP7 + WP1-6	Ad hoc bilateral dialogue - email, zoom or in-person meetings	Input to DEC activities, dialogue on proceedings, alignment	WP7 + WP1-6 leaders and project manager	WP7
WP7 + UCPH WP1-5 project team	Ad hoc bilateral dialogue - email, zoom or in-person meetings	Input to DEC activities, dialogue on proceedings, alignment	WP7 leader, local UCPH WP contributors and project manager	WP7

WP7 + WP6 and WP8	Ad hoc bilateral dialogue and meetings	Coordination between WP6 and WP7. Update WP7 progress to WP8	WP7 leader and project manager	Joint responsibility
4EU+ Communication Group and PR	Every second week (online), occasional face-to-face meetings	Synergy and coherence between TRAIN4EU and 4EU+ communication	WP7 and 4EU+ Communication Group and PR	4EU+ Communication Group and PR
MS Teams – WP7	Ad hoc	Repository tool for sharing DEC documents	WP7 + WP1-8 leaders and project manager	WP7

Online management and monitoring

The dialogue between partners involved in the TRAIN4EU project is framed as online meetings, which in this initial phase of the TRAIN4EU and under pandemic circumstances have proven its worth in supporting the implementation and development of the project.

These learnings will act as a background/basis for a continuously flexible and agile approach in sharing knowledge as well as managing and monitoring a work package via online meetings. Online activity ensures synergy and coherence between the Alliance partners and participants when meeting regularly on Zoom as well as communicating on MS Teams, where WP groups share files, documents and inputs in public as well as closed channels.

Schedule for planning & implementing dissemination, exploitation & communication

The schedule for implementation of the DEC plan is enclosed as annex 1. The schedule will be subject to change in terms of adjusted and revised dissemination, exploitation and communication activities during the project according to the Grant Agreement and Description of the Action.

- Activities autumn 2021

Based on the results of the submitted protocols on baselining and analysis of best practices from WP1-5, these first findings are disseminated to internal stakeholders in the autumn of 2021 using the 4EU+ website and emails as communication channels.

- News for the internal stakeholders via
 - 4EU+/TRAIN4EU website
 - Targeted distribution to the partner universities in the 4EU+ Alliance on activities reflecting the DEC plan's main objective to raise awareness about the value and potential of TRAIN4EU among internal and external stakeholders, staff and colleagues at partner universities.

It is expected that the news will reach several hundred staff members at each university.

8. Outputs and outcomes for TRAIN4EU

TRAIN4EU DEC planned outputs include (M13-35):

- DEC plans:
 - First & second update of DEC Plan (D7.2 & D7.3)
 - Stakeholder mapping & prioritized target groups
- Conferences & webinars
 - 4EU+ Conference on Educational & Research Infrastructure 8 June 2022 & relevant DEC activities
 - TRAIN4EU WP4 / 4EU+ Webinar “Transfer from Academia to Business and Society” on 27. November 2023
 - SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 in Bruxelles on 30. Nov.-1.Dec 2023 (TRAIN4EU in the organizing committee) & relevant DEC activities
- Web presence
 - Draft on a stronger web, SEO, new structure of content and a baseline for web performance
 - Content generation for TRAIN4EU site on 4eu+ website
- News
 - TRAIN4EU WP1-6 news items on 4eu+ newsletter
 - Dedicated TRAIN4EU edition of 4eu+ newsletter

Impact

The TRAIN4EU project runs for three years but aims for a lasting impact in transforming the research and innovation support in the Alliance and beyond after the end of the project.

Every WP leader is responsible for the findings and results in each work package, which is the core of the project; the concrete elements within research support and agendas that can transform the Alliance and beyond.

The DEC implementation plan is a tool designed to maximise the impact of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities in the short and long term. In close co-operation between WP7 and WP1-6 leaders concrete ambitions for impact within the DEC activities are identified and set as described in phase III and IV.

Shared learnings on impact assessment in European University Alliances will also be taken into account. As the 4EU+ Communication Group represents a great repository of knowledge within all areas of communication, alignment and dialogue between the group and WP7 on impact is a given.

Expected outcomes

The expected outcome of each DEC activity has the DEC plan objectives as guidelines. Ambitions for every activity are set in phase II & III within expected categories such as

- Information/media statistics (numbers of publications, traffic, views and shared posts as well as uptake of information by other online activity)
- Stakeholder/target group statistics (number of relevant participants at conferences, workshops, webinars, theme days, etc.)

A list of the TRAIN4EU DEC plan outcomes will be available in Deliverable 7.4 Documentation of Dissemination and Deliverable 7.5 Publications on lessons learned and best practices (M36).

ANNEX I: TENTATIVE IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

Phase I (January – June 2021)

- Deliverable 7.1 Draft DEC Plan (M6)

The DEC activities for phase I may include one or more of the following:

Dissemination	Exploitation	Communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kick-off meeting 13-14 January 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News on TRAIN4EU kick-off meeting 13-14 January • Establish TRAIN4EU page on 4EU+ website

Phase II (July 2021 – December 2022)

- Deliverable 7.2 DEC Plan first update (M24)
- Deliverable 7.6 Policy brief 1 (M18)

The DEC activities for phase II may include one or more of the following:

Dissemination	Exploitation	Communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter, targeted to relevant stakeholders • 4EU+ Visioning conference (final Erasmus+ 'European Universities' project (EUP) conference) on promotion and dissemination of EUP and TRAIN4EU results • 'Forum of European Universities' meeting • Seminars and workshops • National, local dialogue with internal and external relevant stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy brief • Policy Dialogue Meetings with European Commission 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance and strengthening of webpage, targeted information, integration of TRAIN4EU on new 4EU+ website • Contribution to 4EU+ periodical newsletter • Contribution to social media channels • Monitoring on published news and dissemination activity – follow-up on feedback from stakeholders • Use of #TRAIN4EU

Prior to dissemination activities in phase II are: • Stakeholder mapping • Cases to disseminate – initial dissemination activities to be decided • Setting tentative ambitions for the outcome of dissemination, exploitation and communication • Alternative online or hybrid solutions to planned physical activities. All through a co-creative and transparent process.

Phase III (January 2023 – December 2023)

- Deliverable 7.3 DEC Plan second update (M35)
- Deliverable 7.4 Documentation of dissemination of project results through various platforms and selected channels to specific and general audiences

- Deliverable 7.5 Publications on lessons learned and best practices as well as policy briefs on R&I transformations aimed at internal and external decision-makers within education and research sectors (M36)
- Deliverable 7.7 Policy brief 2 (M36)

The DEC activities for phase III may include one or more of the following:

Dissemination	Exploitation	Communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter to relevant stakeholders • Participation in conferences, synergy meetings, meetings & exchanges etc. between European and international university alliances • Publications/reports • Webinars • National, local dialogue with relevant internal and external stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Piloting transformative processes in 4EU+ • Collaboration between European University Alliances on best practices and lessons learned etc. • Policy advice and recommendations for policy makers, EC etc. • Policy briefs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance of website • Contribution to 4EU+ periodical newsletter • Social media • News on website • Stakeholder mapping • Development of key words

Phase IV

End of project and beyond project lifetime

The DEC activities for phase IV may include one or more of the following:

Dissemination	Exploitation	Communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter to relevant stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upscaling of transformative processes • Embedding of best practices, recommendations, and new collaborative practices • Recommendations to sister Alliance partners when engaging in future SwafS projects • Policy advice and recommendations for policymakers, EC etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance of website and social media • News on project evaluation and analysis • Website as a repository for the project

Prior to dissemination activities in phase IV are: • Evaluation of the project • Analysis of the use and implementation of project results • Final analysis of the impact of dissemination, exploitation and communication. All through a co-creative and transparent process.

ANNEX II: 4EU+ COMMUNICATION POLICY

4EU+ Communication policy

Approved by 4EU+ Communications Group and 4EU+ Management Committee on 19/04/2021

Introduction

Policy statement: Effective communication is seen as fundamental in the development of the 4EU+ Alliance and key in building its visibility and recognition among the communities of 4EU+ member universities and external stakeholders, including the EU institutions, national and governmental institutions, universities, other European University alliances and actors on the European and international higher education scene. 4EU+ Alliance is committed to an open and inclusive approach to communication and aims to provide a framework through which the Alliance can highlight its strengths, capitalise on its achievements and establish itself as a role model for the transformation of Higher Education in Europe and beyond.

The following document is aimed at:

- defining and ensuring a common understanding of the Alliance's communication and dissemination goals,
- defining the target groups of the Alliance's communication activities (e.g. researchers, students, staff, external stakeholders)
- reiterating 4EU+ communication principles,
- establishing clear processes for sharing information on the Alliance, its activities and achievements efficiently and effectively.

The document is not intended to:

- address concerns and challenges related to the governance and work flows between different bodies and structures of the 4EU+ Alliance as a whole,
- deal with intricacies related to the knowledge management and organisational information processes within the 4EU+ context.

4EU+ communication goals and principles

1) 4EU+ communication goals and target groups

Key communication goals for the 4EU+ Alliance include:

- raising awareness about the 4EU+ Alliance and the benefits of 4EU+ cooperation among students, staff and the wider communities of 4EU+ member universities by providing timely and easily accessible information on the Alliance, its activities and ways to become involved
- boosting the Alliance's visibility and position in the European and the wider international higher education landscape
- showcasing the added value of 4EU+ cooperation by sharing information on the achievements of the 4EU+ Alliance, including its joint projects, initiatives and good practices resulting from inter-institutional exchange, according to different target groups

- stimulating trust building and a sense of community among academic and non-academic staff and students of the 4EU+ Alliance

4EU+ target groups

The following listing order does not imply a ranking or level of importance of any target groups

Internal 4EU+ community

- academic and administrative leadership
- students and doctoral candidates (young researchers)
- academic staff - lecturers, educational experts
- academic staff - researchers
- administrative staff

External audience

- prospective students, doctoral candidates and staff of 4EU+ member universities
- alumni of 4EU+ member universities
- other European University alliances
- European Commission and other EU institutions active in the European Education Area
- ministries and national agencies in charge of Higher Education
- 4EU+ Associated Partners
- Higher Education institutions in Europe and around the world
- broad public

2) Principles of 4EU+ communication

4EU+ communication is guided by the following principles:

- Open communication approach - sharing relevant 4EU+ information across university structures, ensuring it reaches the right recipients (incl. passing information on to those who might not have received it in the first place and translating relevant information to local languages), making sure the students and staff of 4EU+ member universities know where to look for and find information
- Pro-active approach - stimulating interest in the Alliance and its activities among the members of each 4EU+ member university's community, engaging them in 4EU+ communication by acquainting them with 4EU+ communication channels and tools and providing them with an easy way to: (a) inform the people responsible for managing 4EU+ communication channels about the planned meetings, events and activities, (b) share their ideas and content (including pictures, stories and testimonials) via the Sharepoint online form created for this purpose
- Co-creation approach - engaging staff and students of 4EU+ member universities in the collaborative development of 4EU+ content, being receptive to their feedback, remarks and suggestions
- Relevance approach – creating and securing interest in the Alliance among the 4EU+ community by focusing on concrete, relevant and “need-to-know” more than “nice to know” information when communicating internally

Communication governance and decision-making

The organisational structure, responsibilities and decision-making processes of 4EU+ Communications Group, as well as the Group's relationship with other 4EU+ bodies and communications offices at 4EU+ member universities, are defined in the Terms of reference (Annex).

4EU+ content policy

It is essential that any visual form of communication, documentation or information concerning 4EU+ and produced on behalf of 4EU+ respects the corporate image of the Alliance and the 4EU+ branding guidelines. 4EU+ Communications Group provides advice and guidance to staff and students on the appropriate use of 4EU+ branding and monitors communications produced within the Alliance to ensure they comply with the branding guidelines.

The authorisation to use the 4EU+ logo on is given by 4EU+ local offices.

Key terms:

'4EU+ opportunities' defined as opportunities (funding schemes, job or internship offers, etc.) available exclusively for 4EU+ students and staff.

In a similar fashion, **'4EU+ news'** are defined as information concerning recent, ongoing and upcoming 4EU+ activities, achievements of the 4EU+ Alliance, outcomes of its projects and initiatives, as well as information on 4EU+ opportunities available. If a news item is specifically linked to one 4EU+ member university (e.g. if it concerns a particular event that took place at one 4EU+ member university), the local communications office of this university decides whether the information can be classified as 4EU+ news.

4EU+ communication channels

The main 4EU+ communication channels include:

Channel	Short description/address	4EU+ institution responsible for management
4EU+ website	www.4euplus.eu	Charles University (Kristyna Kolinova, 4EU+ local office)
4EU+ newsletter	frequency depending on the content available	University of Warsaw (Marta Brelih-Wasowska, 4EU+ local office)
4EU+ social media	Twitter https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance Facebook https://www.facebook.com/4EUplusAlliance/ LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/company/4euplus Instagram https://www.instagram.com/4euplus_alliance/	University of Warsaw (Katarzyna Jäger and Daiwa Maksimowicz, UW Press Office / Marta Brelih-Wasowska, 4EU+ local office)

The persons responsible for the different 4EU+ communication channels work in close cooperation, ensuring that the content published on each of the platforms is aligned. They are also responsible for the quality of content published.

Any exceptions from these rules should be approved by the 4EU+ Communications Group.

